

The benefits and challenges of mapping for students and teachers: geospatial technologies as a tool in open school education.

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Abstract Geospatial technologies, with an emphasis on mapping, are increasingly being recognized as highly important instructional resources inside open schools. They offer a multitude of benefits for both students and educators, facilitating the development of crucial cognitive abilities such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and spatial literacy while facilitating interdisciplinary learning, enhancing student engagement, and fostering collaborative opportunities. Nevertheless, the incorporation of technology in educational settings presents other obstacles, including the necessity for adequate teacher preparation, the restricted availability of technological resources, and the possibility of diverting students' attention.

The study incorporates enlightening case studies from a variety of schools, showcasing the successful integration of mapping through the CONNECT project, which encompasses a range of educational settings from special education to experimental and model high schools. These instances demonstrate the potential of mapping to stimulate student-centered learning, foster problem-solving skills, and promote critical thinking by tackling real-world situations via the lens of spatial thinking.

In summary, this article highlights the significant importance of geospatial technology while recognizing inherent constraints and challenges. It is imperative to prioritize ongoing teacher assistance, promote a harmonious integration of technology, and ensure equal opportunities for all students. Through the use and integration of new technologies, students have the opportunity to develop and acquire essential skills that will be vital in a future society that largely depends on digital tools.

Keywords

Geospatial technologies, open schools, maps, problem-solving, spatial thinking, educational resources, future skills.

1. Introduction

Geospatial technologies, encompassing mapping and spatial analysis tools, have gained significant prominence in educational settings. GIS is listed among the 25 most important technological innovations that influenced the development of humanity in the 20th century [10]. The utilization of visual representation in education is a potent instrument that enables students to graphically depict concepts, ideas, and relationships, so facilitating their comprehension and retention of information. The integration of active learning techniques enhances students' engagement in the learning process, resulting in enhanced levels of comprehension.

Open education, which is distinguished by its adaptable and non-conventional learning frameworks, has observed the incorporation of these technologies due to their provision of a diverse range of advantages for both students and educators; while processing the stages CARE – KNOW-DO. Nevertheless, the process of integrating this educational approach is not devoid of its own unique set of obstacles, encompassing issues such as the requirement for comprehensive teacher preparation and the imperative need to guarantee fair and impartial accessibility for every student. Open schooling was introduced mostly with regards to science education and public engagement; there was a strong collaboration between academic/research members (universities, museums and research centers), non-academic

/research members (schools and local communities) and teaching staff [12]. Open schooling has a lot of dimensions and the most known indicators for monitoring are the following ones: science education, public engagement, open access, gender equality, ethics, governance [8]. Collaboration and communication are key components of this process, facilitating the creation of concept maps, mind maps, and the utilization of advanced technologies such as GEOspatial Artificial Intelligence (GEOAI) to enhance comprehension of spatial thinking, data analysis, and interactive visualization. Consequently, these approaches contribute to the cultivation of a comprehensive and all-encompassing learning experience. Open learning is all about removing “unnecessary barriers” to learning and about an opening of learning opportunities by adopting a flexible approach to key dimensions like time, place, pace, enrolment, accreditation, etc [2]. Teachers need to offer opportunities for their students to critically analyse maps as part of powerful geography instruction in order to help them become well-informed and civic-minded citizens [6]. When school’s projects meet the real needs of the community; for which leaders, teachers, students and the local community share responsibility, over which they share authority and from which they all benefit through [11].

2. Advantages of Mapping in Open School Education

There are many advantages of using geosciences in open schooling. As Kerski mentions "the power of a GIS is that it allows us to ask questions of data"[4]. Students using this inquiry approach form research questions, develop a methodology, gather and analyze data, and draw conclusions, but there are much more benefits as mentioned at the Table 1 [4].

Table 1. Benefits to GIS implementation

Benefit to GIS Implementation	Φ	σ	Degree of Benefit				
			None 1	2	Some 3	4	Very Much 5
Helps teach national, state, or district standards.	3.05	1.35			B		
Enhances Learning.	3.97	1.07				B	
Provides exploratory tool for data analysis.	4.06	1.17					B
Provides employment skills.	3.32	1.34			B		
Offers team learning environment.	3.58	1.25			B		
Provides real-world relevance to subject.	4.14	1.13					B
Provides integration of different subjects.	3.72	1.17				B	
Provides opportunities to partner with community.	3.46	1.41			B		
Enhances motivation and student interest.	3.95	1.13					B

2.1. Augmented Cognitive Processes and Analytical Abilities

The utilization of mapping techniques in education fosters the development of critical thinking skills and the ability to interpret geographical data among students. Students acquire the ability to analyse maps, recognize recurring patterns, and derive logical inferences, so refining their aptitude for problem-solving. Furthermore, they cultivate technological and digital skills. Through the exploration of geographical information, students are able to cultivate a more profound comprehension of intricate real-world matters.

2.2. Facilitation of Interdisciplinary Learning

Geospatial technologies serve as a means to foster interdisciplinary learning by establishing connections between many academic disciplines, including geography, mathematics, and science. Mapping projects provide students with the opportunity to delve into a diverse array of subjects, so promoting a comprehension of interrelated ideas. Contribute to a high-quality geography curriculum centred on the development of powerful knowledge [14]. These standards specifically advocate for the use of “problem-solving” geospatial technologies such as geographical information systems (GIS), global positioning system (GPS), and remote sensing as teaching and learning tools to create meaningful, authentic, and engaging social studies lessons [1]. Geographical research justifies, there are three

rationalities that deliver GIS to enter into education, namely: 1) educational justification, supporting geography and environmental education teaching and learning; 2) Justification of the workplace: GIS is an important tool for knowledge workers in the 21st century; and 3) Justification based on place: GIS is an ideal tool for use in studying geographical problems on various scales [9]. Research also agrees that the implementation of GIS in education throughout the world has been developed in two main lines, namely, "teaching about GIS" and "teaching with GIS" [9]. The first is related to teaching GIS as the main subject and the other as a tool that can be useful in any of the subjects of the open school curriculum. The interdisciplinary learning is an efficient way to bring students' best practice and to create actions.

2.3. Enhanced Student Engagement

Engagement poses a frequently encountered obstacle in the realm of education; yet, the implementation of mapping techniques presents a potential remedy. GIS is also a powerful technology for geography teachers at the pre-college level; with this new tool, students can engage in serious inquiry about issues of local and global significance using authentic data [5]. GIS is defined as an instructional tool that facilitates students' engagement in inquiry and their understanding of geography and improves their skills in geographical analysis and reasoning [10]. The utilization of interactive maps and data visualization tools has the ability to attract the attention of students, hence enhancing the engagement level during lessons and fostering a sense of curiosity towards discovery. As students learned more about local community events, people, and historical forces, they became increasingly engaged with the material and enthusiastic about making connections to larger issues and processes [7]. Student involvement is obvious to any type of school that GIS projects are implemented (model high schools, experimental schools or in special education schools).

2.4. Promotion of Collaborative Efforts

Mapping projects frequently entail the participation of multiple individuals, thereby fostering a culture of collaboration among students. Individuals acquire the skills necessary to engage in successful communication, exchange ideas, and collaboratively construct complete maps, so equipping themselves for future pursuits that need joint effort. Using GIS alone does not guarantee better geographical learning, but it has the potential to become an influential tool when combined with powerful pedagogies and the role of the geography teacher is crucial in making this link [14]. In interactive teaching the instructor elaborates on students' comments and expands their thinking through fostering conversation about a particular topic [7]. Finally, it allows young people the space to imagine themselves as members of an ongoing community [7].

Figure 1. The enquiry process in geography (items shown in blue could be supported using GIS)

It is also helpful in understanding how they learn critical thinking about geographies and histories over time and in concert with others, including both their peers and their teachers [15].

3. Challenges of incorporating mapping in open school education

3.1. Continual Professional development for educators and provision of assistance

Teachers have a crucial and indispensable role in effectively using mapping technologies into educational settings. In order to ensure effective implementation in the classroom, it is imperative that educators get ongoing training to be abreast of the most current tools and practices. The integration of GIS into the teaching of geography is complicated by many factors highlighted in numerous studies and often requires a great deal of personal involvement from the teacher [10]. This is because most teachers have not had a formal education in GIS [10]. In any case, the latest trends in GIS are web-based GIS applications; which are really easy to be used and to be familiarized. Story Maps are easy to create and use, and they do not require users to have special knowledge of computer programming [1].

3.2. Restricted availability of technological resources

Not all educational institutions have access to technological resources. The difficulty of ensuring equitable access to geospatial technology for all students, irrespective of their socio-economic status, persists. Furthermore, there are more and more OpenSource or freely available GIS programs and GIS databases or web GIS services on smartphones and tablets, which has reduced the occurrence of software and technical problems for geography teachers [10]. Story Maps are Esri's Web-based GIS platform, ArcGIS Online; which combine interactive maps with stories to tell spatial narratives and digital stories [1]. Story Maps use geography to organize and present information [1]. To tell the story of a place, users create maps by linking "interactive maps with rich content text, photos, video, and audio" to build an environment that actively engages users [1].

3.3. The Perils of Electronic Distractions

In the contemporary era of technology, the presence of electronic distractions has the potential to hinder the process of acquiring knowledge and skills. Educators require effective methodologies to manage the various distractions that may arise while simultaneously leveraging the advantages offered by mapping technologies. For example, during CONNECT maps scenarios have been implemented successfully in open schooling. A scenario may depend on several dimensions which describe different learning situations: the learning domain (course topic), the learner (his know-how and knowledge levels), the tutor/teacher, the learning and tutoring activities (their typology, organization and coordination), the

activity distribution among learners, teachers and computers, the learning “procedures” according to a particular school/institution/ university and the didactical / pedagogical environment [3]. In other words, dimensions are closely related: changing one dimension leads to the change of others [3].

3.4. The obstacles faced by students

Within the educational setting, students frequently face a multitude of obstacles while engaging with the concepts of mapping and spatial learning. One such challenge pertains to spatial cognition, which necessitates the capacity to construct and comprehend the interconnections among entities and ideas within a spatial framework. Data interpretation is a significant challenge for students, since they are required to engage with intricate datasets and unravel their underlying importance. Collaboration might provide difficulties, as it requires the proficient utilization of communication and teamwork abilities. Time management is a frequently encountered challenge, particularly among students who must effectively allocate their time between mapping projects and other academic assignments. In addition, the effort of effectively organizing information inside maps can be perceived as challenging. For many individuals, lacking proficiency in technology might amplify these difficulties, as technical constraints and aversion to change serve as further obstacles to adopting mapping tools and processes. These limitations underscore the significance of implementing comprehensive support and educational initiatives to enable students in surmounting these barriers and effectively leveraging the advantages of mapping in their educational endeavours.

4. Case studies: Mapping Integration in Open Schools

This section presents case studies from various open schools, illustrating successful mapping integration through the CONNECT projects. Some of the below case studies encompass different types of open schools, including special education institutions, experimental high schools, and model high schools. They showcase how mapping can foster student-centered learning, problem-solving, critical thinking, and real-world issue resolution.

4.1. 1st Professional High School of Lefkada

The first Professional High school of Lefkada combined different projects of CONNECT in order to investigate climate change and shoreline erosion by using the technology of GIS (QGIS) as a case study at the island of Lefkada, Greece. Their final conclusions were continuous monitoring of the phenomenon using satellite images and drones in order to predict the evolution of the phenomenon in time [13], Figure 2.

Figure 2. Landsat data analysis

4.2. The model high school of Heraklion

The model high school of Heraklion used a web-based GIS technology (Story Maps), the CONNECT procedures of CARE – KNOW – DO in order to visualize their school's accessibility. They investigated if anything more is needed, their school's benefits and challenges. Students find out the positive and negative spots around their school and fixed a relevant story map in order to inform and motivate locals and all members of school community (Figure 3) [16]. They concluded that it will be necessary to implement modifications within the school premises to ensure accessibility for those using wheelchairs, enabling them to navigate between different levels of the building. Further changes also with an inclusion of a ramp at the east entrance of the educational institution, together with the construction of a walkway encircling the premises. So the educational institution currently lacks the necessary infrastructure to accommodate individuals with special needs, necessitating the implementation of appropriate interventions.

Figure 3. Positive and negative spots around the school

4.3. 1st Syros High School – Experimental

The 1st Syros High School – Experimental conducted an interactive map by utilizing Google Maps in order to create an alternative map for visitors of their island. They generated different proposals, assessed and optimized them, and collected additional data using drones. The suggested plan is depicted in Figure 4. [17].

Figure 4. Interactive map of Syros

All mentioned case studies demonstrate the potential of mapping to facilitate student-centered learning, promote problem-solving skills, encourage critical thinking, and enable the resolution of real-world issues. The CONNECT project provided numerous schools in Greece with the possibility to create open schooling scenarios through the utilization of geosciences technology.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, it is evident that geospatial technologies play a significant role in influencing the development of open schooling. These tools possess the capacity to fundamentally transform the methods by which students acquire knowledge and teachers deliver instruction. The significance of educators in facilitating the effective incorporation of geospatial tools within educational settings cannot be underestimated. By means of their leadership and steadfast dedication to continuous professional development, educators have the ability to unleash the complete capabilities of modern technologies, thereby cultivating not just fundamental digital proficiencies but also promoting spatial cognition, data literacy, critical reasoning, and collaborative aptitudes inside their students.

Open schools are at the forefront of adopting novel ways in the quickly expanding educational ecosystem. Geospatial technologies provide novel insights, enhanced comprehension, and a means to provide students with essential skills necessary for their future roles as adults. The incorporation of geospatial technologies, namely mapping, into open school instruction has substantial implications. Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognize and address the challenges that are intrinsically associated with this methodology. This study emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development for educators, guaranteeing equitable access to technology, and a commitment to advancing and prioritizing the integration of geospatial technologies. Educational institutions that remain accessible to students possess the capacity to provide them with the essential competencies required in an increasingly technology-driven and spatially-oriented world. As we progress, it is imperative to uphold and advocate for the integration of geospatial technologies in education, acknowledging their capacity to not only equip students for an increasingly digital era but also to cultivate a comprehensive skill set that will be advantageous in a dynamic global landscape. Collectively, it is within our capacity to guarantee the preservation of open schooling as a symbol of pioneering advancements and exceptional standards in the field of education.

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